

MaxEnt Versus $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is so closely linked to an ideal gas as well as to MaxEnt (maximum entropy subject to constraints) that one might associate properties of interactions in the gas with MaxEnt in general. We argue that MaxEnt solutions may exist which do not conform to the interactions of the ideal gas. In particular, we argue that for an ideal gas: $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ ((1)) for physical reasons and this relation automatically yields $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ or $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ for entropy. As a result, it might seem that maximum entropy subject to the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ ((2)) is equivalent to ((1)). We argue here that this is only one case. Maximum entropy for the constraints ((2)) has two solutions, and only one corresponds to ((1)), namely $F = \ln(p)$ for entropy = $-\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. As a result, $\ln(p)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann case of F is linked with one kind of maximization of entropy and certain physical reactions and not necessarily with all cases of MaxEnt subject to the constraints ((2)).

In particular, we argue that the Tsallis type of distribution also follows from MaxEnt with ((2)), but does not allow for ((1)). This might mean that one does not have a picture of colliding independent particles forming the equilibrium. We thus suggest MaxEnt is more general than the physical independent two particle collision picture which makes sense for an ideal gas, but might not cover all physical situations (i.e. a Tsallis case).

The Physical Case for $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$

Given an ideal gas of independent particles at equilibrium, one may note that physically one has elastic collisions. It seems physically reasonable that:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) = p(e_i+e_j) \text{ if } e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \quad ((3))$$

If there are N particles, then $Np(e_i)$ = the number of particles with e_i and it seems that interactions involving e_i should be proportional to this number. There has been no mention of maximum entropy. In fact, one may solve ((3)) to find

$$p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((4))$$

As a result, it seems that there is no reason to even consider the notion of entropy in the ideal gas case. Nevertheless, one might suggest that the constraint ((2)) involves two pieces of information, namely $p(e_i)$ and the two moments e_i power 0 and e_i power 1. If one wished to consolidate these two into one form, one might create:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) \text{ with } F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + d \quad (-1/T \text{ and } d \text{ are constants}) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is a minimal information form. We showed in (1) that if one changes $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, the constraints ((2)) display two types of information and do not constrain them into one, like $F(p)$ does. This means that this constraint in $p F(p)$ manifests itself when one expands

$$(p+dp) F_1(p+dp) \rightarrow \text{first order in } dp \quad dp F(p) + p dF_1(p) + p dp dF/dp \quad ((6))$$

Here $dF_1/dp \rightarrow dF/dp$ because dp already exists in the third term of the RHS of ((6))

What is $F_1(p)$? F_1 is the inverse function of $p+dp$, i.e.

$$F_1(p+dp) = -e_i/T + b \quad ((7))$$

The question is whether in $F_1(p) = F(p) + \text{correction}$, the correction is of the order of dp or smaller. We assume

$$dp F(p) + p dF_1(p) \text{ approx} = (-e_i/T + \text{constant}) dp$$

A first solution is:

$$p dF/dp = 1 \quad ((8)) \quad \text{or } F = \ln(p) \quad \text{because } F(p) = -e_i/T + b \text{ and one simply adds a constant.}$$

Then $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, the solution found above through collision considerations.

How does one see ((1)) $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ in this solution strictly from the condition ((8))? It is known that $\ln(a*b) = \ln(a)+\ln(b)$, but we wish to see what is happening in terms of the derivative condition.

$$F(p(e+de)) = -1/T (e+de) + b_1$$

$$\text{For simplicity consider } F(p(e+de)) = e+de \text{ and } F(p(e)) = e$$

$$F\{ p(e) (1+1/p dp/de de) \} = F(p(e_i)) + F(p(de))$$

$$\text{If } F(1+1/p dp/de de) = F(p(de)) = de = 1/p dp/de de [dF/dp \text{ (at } p=1)] \quad ((9))$$

then one would have a product rule ((1)). This would require that $F(1) = 0$, (no statistical uncertainty). $dF/dp = 1/p$ evaluated at $p=1$ yields 1 so $dp/de = p$ constant or

$$p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((10))$$

A general maximum entropy solution, however, will not yield this result. Instead of having:

$$p dF/dp = 1 \text{ one could have } p dF/dp = a_1 e_i + a_2 \quad ((11))$$

This leads to $dF/(a_3F + a_4) = dp/p$ or $F = a_5 p^{a_3} + a_6$ ((12))

((12)) is a Tsallis form solution which does not satisfy ((1)). In other words, maximum entropy subject to the usual constraints ((2)) does not always result in reactions of the form of those which occur in an ideal gas.

Consider $F = a + b p^k$ then $p = (1-ke)^{1/k}$ ((13))

$dF/dp = bk p^{k-1}$ $dp/de = -kp/(1-ke) = -kk/ln(p)$ ((14))

$F(p(1+1/p dp/de de)) = F(p) + de(-k)/ln(p) = a_1e+a_2 + (a_3e+a_4) de(-k)/ln(p)$ ((15))

$F(1+1/p dp/de de) = F(1) + 1/p dp/de de dF/dp$

But $p dF/dp = a_3e + a_4$ $F(1)=a+b$

$1/pp dp/de (pdF/dp) = (a_3e+a_4) (-kkp)/ln(p) 1/pp$ which does not match $-kk/ln(p) (a_3e+a_4)$ of ((15))

and so ((1)) does not hold. In other words, even though the constraints are still ((2)), the distribution must be created in a manner quite different physically from what is implied by two body elastic collisions or ((1)).

Thus, maximum entropy subject to the usual constraints ((2)) does not necessarily mean ((1)). ((1)) applies to a very specific kind of interaction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be solved using MaxEnt subject to the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = Eave$ or $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$. The latter describes the physical interactions in the system and one may use it to find $p(e_i)=Cexp(-e_i/T)$ without any notion of entropy. It may be shown that this solution is a minimal information solution, if one consolidates the two pieces of information into the form $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ such that $F(p(e_i))= ae_i+b$. We show, however, that maximum entropy subject to the two constraints allows for two types of solutions and only one, $F =ln(p)$, allows for $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$. This product probability type of interaction is a special kind of maximum entropy, but not all maximum entropy cases, even with the same constraints satisfy this condition.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on the Maximum Entropy Approach (preprint, zenodo, 2026)

